

PLANT NUTRITION, THE PROCESS OF ABSORPTION**Saitkulov Foziljon Ergashevich¹****Eshqobilov Javoxir Fazliddin o'g'li²****Turgunova Nasiba Sheralibek qizi³****Ikromova E'zozabonu Orif qizi⁴****Xamidov Asadbek Iqboljon o'g'li⁵**¹Tashkent State Agrarian University,²⁻³⁻⁴⁻⁵Student of Tashkent State Agrarian University<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7451056>

Annotation: Depending on the source of the absorbed carbon, there are several types of plant nutrition. Most of the lower plants, all fungi and most of the bacteria, can use carbon only from organic compounds in which it is contained in a reduced form.

Key words: Nutrition, carbon (C), oxygen (O), hydrogen (H), nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), sulfur (S), potassium (K), calcium (Ca), magnesium (Mg), iron (Fe)

INTRODUCTION

Plant nutrition, the process of absorption and assimilation by plants from the environment of chemical elements necessary for their life; consists in the movement of substances from the environment into the cytoplasm of plant cells and their chemical transformation into compounds peculiar to this plant species. Absorption and assimilation of nutrients (anabolism) together with their breakdown and excretion (catabolism) constitute metabolism (metabolism) — the basis of the vital activity of the body.

Almost all chemical elements existing on Earth have been found in the composition of plants. However, only the following are necessary for plant Nutrition: carbon (C), oxygen (O), hydrogen (H), nitrogen (N), phosphorus (P), sulfur (S), potassium (K), calcium (Ca), magnesium (Mg), iron (Fe) and trace elements: boron (B), manganese (Mn), zinc (Pb), copper (Cu), molybdenum (Mo), etc. The batteries are absorbed from the air in the form of carbon dioxide (CO₂) and from the soil in the form of water (H₂O) and mineral salt ions. In higher terrestrial plants, aerial or leaf nutrition is distinguished (see Photosynthesis) and soil, or root, nutrition (see Mineral nutrition of plants). Lower plants (bacteria, fungi, algae) absorb CO₂, H₂O and salts throughout the body surface.

METHOD AND RESULTS

The need of the plant organism for various elements is not the same; the greatest is in oxygen and hydrogen. This is explained by the fact that a living plant consists of 80-90% water, i.e. oxygen and hydrogen in a ratio of 8:1. In

addition, the plant consumes hundreds of times more water during its life during transpiration than its own mass (to prevent overheating). The basis of the dry matter of the plant, along with carbon (45%), is also oxygen (42%) and hydrogen (6-7%). The share of mineral nutrition elements, among which nitrogen and potassium predominate, accounts for only 5-7% of the dry matter of the plant. No element of nutrition can be replaced by another (the so-called principle of irreplaceability of nutrients). The absence or great lack of any of them inevitably leads to the cessation of growth and to the death of the plant. Each of the elements performs its unique function in plant tissues, which is inextricably linked with all other functions of the body. Thus, carbon, together with hydrogen and oxygen, forms the basis of all molecules of organic compounds (see Biogenic elements). Substances consisting only of these three elements (carbohydrates) are the main substrate of respiration. The shells of plant cells also consist of polymer carbohydrates. Each species and even variety of plants absorbs mainly those elements that are needed in the greatest quantities for its characteristic metabolism. Therefore, for example, the potassium content in plants is usually ten times higher than the sodium content, although in soils the relationship between these elements is the opposite. Some plant species are able to accumulate rare elements in their tissues (for example, lanthanum), which they use in geological exploration (see Indicator plants).

Depending on the source of the absorbed carbon, there are several types of plant nutrition. Most of the lower plants (all fungi and most of the bacteria) can use carbon only from organic compounds in which it is contained in a reduced form. When such compounds are oxidized during respiration, the chemical energy stored in them is released, which can then be spent on various endergonic (i.e. energy-consuming) processes: synthesis of more complex compounds, movement of substances in the plant, etc. Nutrition of this type is called heterotrophic, and plants that consume organic carbon sources are heterotrophic (see Heterotrophic organisms); nutrition due to dead organic residues is called saprophytic, and plants that feed on dead organic residues are saprophytes. This type of nutrition is characteristic of all putrefactive fungi and bacteria. Heterotrophs living off organic compounds, etc. living organisms are called parasites. These include all fungi and bacteria — pathogens of animal and plant diseases, as well as some higher plants, for example, the infestation, which sucks the juices of other plants with the help of special suckers. Parasitic plant nutrition differs from symbiosis, in which there is a constant exchange of waste products, useful for both partners. Symbiotic plant nutrition is observed, for

example, in nitrogen-fixing bacteria that settle in nodules on the roots of legumes (see Nitrogen fixation), in cap fungi whose hyphae penetrate into the root tissues of woody plants (see Mycorrhiza), as well as in lichens, which are a group of fungi that are in constant cohabitation with algae. Most plants are able to absorb carbon from carbon dioxide, reducing it to organic compounds. This type of nutrition is called autotrophic (see Autotrophic organisms). It is characteristic of all higher green plants, as well as algae, some bacteria. The reduction of CO₂ to organic compounds requires energy expenditure either due to absorbed sunlight (photosynthetics), or due to the oxidation of reduced compounds absorbed from the external environment (chemosynthetics).

CONCLUSION

Thanks to Plant nutrition, a large biogeochemical cycle of substances in nature is realized. Autotrophic (mainly green, or photosynthetic) plants give rise to this cycle by removing CO₂ from the atmosphere and creating organic substances rich in chemical energy. Heterotrophic plants (mainly saprophytes) close this cycle, decomposing dead organic residues to the original mineral substances.

In the process of photosynthesis, plants not only absorb substances, but also accumulate energy. One of the primary products of photosynthesis is sugar. When 6 gram molecules of CO₂ and the same amount of H₂O are combined, 1 gram molecule of glucose (180 g) is formed. This process occurs with the absorption of 674 kcal (1 kcal = 4.19 kj) of sunlight energy, which is stored in the chemical bonds of sugar. Together with sugar molecules, this stored chemical energy can then move to other, non-photosynthetic parts of plants, for example, to the root. Here, in the process of respiration, it can be released for the synthesis of more complex compounds and for other vital processes of plant cells. Although only CO₂ and H₂O are directly involved in photosynthesis, for its implementation and especially for the subsequent transformations of its primary products, all other elements are necessary, no matter in what negligible quantities they are contained in the plant.

Transformations of nutrients occur in various organs and tissues and are connected with each other in a continuous cycle of substances in the plant organism. In the leaves, during photosynthesis, primary organic products (assimilates) are formed from CO₂ in the air and H₂O coming from the root. One of them is sucrose, a universal form of carbohydrate transportation. From the photosynthetic cells of the leaf, sucrose enters a special transport system — sieve-shaped phloem tubes, which ensure the downward movement of substances first along the leaf veins, and then along the conductive bundles of

the stem to the root. Here the assimilates leave the sieve tubes and spread through the root tissues. Water and mineral salt ions move towards the assimilates flowing from the leaves, which first bind to the surface of the root cells, and then penetrate into the cells through the cell membrane. At the same time, some elements (potassium, sodium, to a large extent calcium, magnesium, etc.) arrive in pasoka and are fed to aboveground bodies in an unchanged state. Others (for example, nitrogen), meeting with the centrifugal flow of assimilates, interact with it, becoming part of organic compounds (amino acids and amides), and in such a modified form enter pasoka. Finally, the third (such as phosphorus), passing through the root tissues, are also included in organic compounds (nucleotides, phosphoric esters of sugars), but then, again splitting off, enter the pasoka mainly in the form of free ions. One way or another, the elements of the root nutrition of plants, together with water, enter the vessels of the xylem — the second transport system of the plant, which ensures the upward movement of substances to the aboveground organs. The movement of water and substances dissolved in it through the vessels occurs due to root pressure and transpiration. In the leaf, these substances from the vessels penetrate into photosynthetic cells, where their secondary interaction with assimilates occurs. At the same time, the most diverse organic and organo-mineral compounds are formed, from which, after a number of complications, new plant organs develop.

The role of nutrition. Plant nutrition provides the following processes with substances and energy: maintenance of vital activity (compensation for loss of nutrients during respiration and excretion into the external environment), growth of organs, deposition of substances in reserve and, finally, reproduction of offspring (formation of fruits and seeds). With insufficient nutrition of plant nutrients, processes related to vital activity and reproduction of offspring are provided first of all. With a moderate lack of nutrition, the plant grows young parts of the plant (upper leaves, root endings) it still continues due to reutilization, i.e. reuse of nutrients by their outflow from older leaves. With a sharp lack of nutrition, the plant growth stops, and all nutritional resources are directed to the main function of the plant organism — reproduction of offspring. Under these conditions, barley, for example, has a height of only 4-5 cm, but forms 2-3 quite normal grains. An excess of certain elements of plant nutrition is as harmful as their lack.

Creating the best conditions for soil nutrition of plants by irrigation and fertilization is the most effective means of crop management of agricultural

plants. In closed ground (greenhouses, greenhouses), it is also possible to regulate the air temperature by changing the CO₂ content in the air and additional lighting (see Plant light culture).

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